

Effect of DC Tests on Induced Space Charge

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ABSTRACT

Poling-induced space charges in peeled samples of ac aged/dc tested cables were studied using the thermal pulse technique. Samples were poled at ~ 0.12 MV/cm for 3.5 hours at 70°C using the same polarity as that used for the dc tests. Previous work seemed to indicate that dc testing could have permanent effects which could be detected by the amount of poling-induced charge. An attempt was made to examine this by using three samples with about the same length of ac aging but with different amounts of dc testing. The sample with one dc test and the sample with 23 dc tests were appreciably oxidized whereas the sample with 11 dc tests was not oxidized. Other interesting observations were made. When the sample was pulsed from the face exposed to the positive poling electrode, a negative space charge was observed. When pulsed from the opposite face, a positive space charge was observed. The space charge decay was found to be asymmetric. At 70°C , the negative space charge decays faster than the positive space charge. At 60°C , the decay was observed to be about the same on both sides. When the poling field is small, both sides have a positive space charge. For larger poling fields, the space charge in the film close to the positive electrode is negative.

INTRODUCTION

An earlier report from our laboratories [1] indicated that the space charge which could be induced by poling samples cut from aged cable insulation might be a diagnostic tool for determining the degree of cable aging. This thesis is supported by Das Gupta et al. [2] who have reported that thermally stimulated discharge current and thermal transient current measurements seem to indicate the degree of insulation aging. The present paper reports on the continuing thermal pulse study [3, 4] of the space charging in the cables being aged in the Detroit Edison study.

The experiments for this study were designed to test whether or not the degree of space charge induced could be correlated with the number of times the cable had been stressed with dc. However, the samples with similar AC aging times but with different degrees of dc stressing were found not to be uniform in color. The Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) studies showed that these visual differences were an indication of oxidation. Because of the introduction of this additional variable, the original goal was not achieved. However, interesting observations were made as to the character of the space charge with respect to the poling electrode.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The samples were obtained from the EPRI project at Detroit Edison. Preliminary results have been published [5]. URD type XLPE insulated cables rated at 15 kV were aged under accelerated conditions at 60 Hz, 6 kV/mm (150 V/mil) and load cycled daily to 90°C conductor temperature with water in the conductor and outside the insulation. Testing with dc was at 40 kV with the conductor negative for 15 minutes. Four samples were selected. Sample #1 was ac aged for a total of 591 days and tested once with dc at 199

days. Sample #2 was AC aged for a total of 525 days with 11 dc tests between 199 and 525 days. Sample #3 was ac aged for a total of 525 days with 23 dc tests between 199 and 525 days. Sample #4 was ac aged and not dc tested. Appearance and FTIR indicated that it resembled sample #2 in not being oxidized. All four samples were obtained from the same reel.

Samples were prepared by peeling the insulation using a lathe to provide layer thicknesses of ~ 225 μm [6, 7]. Because the material closer to the conductor would have experienced greater stress, the samples used were taken from the vicinity of the inner semicon (conductor shield). Gold electrodes were evaporated on both sides of the film. Each sample was poled for 10 minutes at 70°C with the side of the film closer to the conductor negative. The poling was, therefore, done using the same polarity seen by the insulation during the dc tests.

Thermal pulse experiments were carried out at NIST using 1 μs duration pulses from a dye laser on samples #1 to #3. Additional TP experiments were carried out on sample #4 at the University of Connecticut. Pulses were applied to both sides of each sample in separate measurements, i.e., the side with the negative poling electrode and the side with the positive poling electrode.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 1(a) and (b) show the FTIR spectra of the samples taken near the inner semicon and near the outer semicon. The spectra labeled #1, #2, and #3 refer to the sample numbers. Sample #1 had had one dc application, sample #2 had had 11 dc applications, and sample #3 had had 23 dc applications. The peak at 1740 cm^{-1} has

Fig. 1 (a) (b). FTIR spectra of samples #1 to #3.

been considered to be due to the antioxidant since preliminary studies have shown that this peak intensity decreases with aging time. The carbonyl peak at 1720 cm^{-1} is only seen for samples #1 and #3. For these cases, the carbonyl peak intensity of the inner insulation is appreciable whereas that of the outer insulation appears to be a small shoulder near the 1740 cm^{-1} peak. Visual inspection showed that these two insulation samples were yellowish colored while #2 was clear. Also, the yellowish color for the insulation closer to the conductor shield was more intense than for the insulation closer to the insulation shield. The 1720 cm^{-1} absorbance was not seen for sample #2 for any part of the insulation. The yellowish color was also not seen in the cross sections of this sample. The yellowish color observed in cable samples #1 and #3 was probably due to oxidation. The insulation closer to the conductor shield reached a higher temperature than that further from the conductor which is consistent with the higher degree of oxidation of this portion of the insulation. However, it is not clear why samples #1 and #3 oxidized in testing whereas sample #2 did not. All three cable samples were originally from the same reel.

Figure 2 shows the intensity of the thermal pulse signal from both cathode and anode sides. Both positive and negative space charges were seen for samples #1 and #3, which were yellowish colored and oxidized. In these samples, the positive space charge was seen on the cathode side and the negative space charge on the anode side. However, for sample #2, which was not yellowish, space charges on both sides were positive. The results indicate that the introduction of carbonyl groups into the insulation makes it easier to form the trapped negative space charge around the anode. Considering these results, the difference of the space charge amount among these three samples is thought to be due to the difference in oxidation rather than the difference in the number of dc applications.

Fig. 2. Initial amplitude of TP signals.

Studies on samples #1 through #3 cut from the aged cables indicated that when the poling field was small, i.e., 0.05 MV/cm at 70°C for 10 minutes, both the cathode and anode side showed a positive space charge. When the poling field was increased to more than 0.15 MV/cm at 70°C for 10 minutes, the positive poled side showed a negative space charge and the negative poled side showed a positive space charge.

In order to survey the temperature and field dependence of the charges near the surfaces, a simplified thermal pulse instrument which is schematically shown in Fig. 3 was assembled at the University of Connecticut. Sample #4 was studied using this apparatus.

Fig. 3. Simplified TP apparatus.

Figure 4 shows the change in thermal pulse current (TPC) signal after poling at 70°C and 0.15 MV/cm for 10 minutes. The sample was cut from a cable which had been aged for 600 days with no dc application. This cable came from the same reel as that for samples #1 through #3. The FTIR and the lack of color indicated that it was not oxidized. The decay of the space charge is shown with the time since the cessation of poling indicated in minutes.

Fig. 4. TPC signals showing decay with time at room temperatures.

According to a photo diode measurement, the xenon light pulse has approximately a $60\text{ }\mu\text{s}$ rise time followed by a duration of about $100\text{ }\mu\text{s}$ before gradually decaying. The TPC signal correlates with the light intensity curve. In Fig. 4, positive and negative charges are seen adjacent to the cathode and anode respectively. The peak values of the TPC signal were plotted with the time after poling to see the decay curve of both positive and negative charges at the temperatures indicated in Fig. 5. The peak values occurred within $150\text{ }\mu\text{s}$. At these short times, only the charge near the surface of the sample is probed. The results are shown in Fig. 5 (a)(b). At 70°C and 80°C the decay of the negative charge is faster than that of the positive charge. The rates of decay of both charges are almost the same at 60°C . It has already been reported [1] that the decay at room temperature was very slow, the decay time to half its original value being on the order of 200 hours.

Fig. 5 (a) (b). Peak amplitude of TPC signals vs. aging time at 60°, 70°, 80°C: (a) thermal pulse applied to poling anode, (b) thermal pulse applied to poling cathode.

The "half decay" time at each temperature is plotted with $1/T$ in Fig. 6(a)(b) to calculate the activation energies of both positive and negative charges. The activation energies were 0.38 eV and 0.84 eV, respectively. These results indicate that the behavior of the heterocharges at the two sides is not symmetric.

Fig. 6 (a) (b). Half decay time of TPC signals vs. $1/T$: (a) positive charge, (b) negative charge.

CONCLUSION

Oxidation in the samples obscured the effects of prior dc testing in the thermal pulse behavior. More work is needed to understand the interplay of temperature, field, and oxidation. At lower poling fields, there seems to be hole injection from the positive electrode. At high fields, the heterocharges at the positive electrode and at the negative electrode seem to be of two different types. That at least a part of this heterocharge is due to carbonyl groups seems indicated by the greater space charge observed in the more oxidized specimens.

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